

Significant deceleration and mission failure, due to dilatant vacuum, expected for the Breakthrough Starshot programme.

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The Breakthrough Starshot project based on ultra-light nanocrafts does not take into account the recently proven dilatancy of the physical vacuum, expressed via a modified Stokes' formula, which successfully passed several tests. The equation indicates that dilatant vacuum will cause mission failure, by provoking a huge negative acceleration of the StarChips due to their ultra-light weight and large radius (of the lightsail). Calculations are presented, which suggest the necessity of resorting to larger masses to reduce the effect of vacuum's viscous force.

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I. Introduction

According to the Breakthrough Starshot project¹, a fleet of StarChips nanocrafts fitted with lightsails, which are centimeter-sized spacecrafts weighing a few grams and propelled by a ground-based laser array, will be sent toward Proxima Centauri B [1]. The strategy of the space mission, whose principles are described in [2], is ultra-light weight combined with a sufficiently large lightsail [3]. According to the designers, this solution will allow the micro spacecrafts to reach 15-20% of the speed of light. However, they do not consider the recently proven dilatancy of physical vacuum [4]. Once the StarChips characteristics and the expected speed are put into the equations for dilatant vacuum, which have been verified via several tests using NASA's data and relativity, a strong deceleration is predicted, causing mission failure. In Sect.II the equations of dilatant vacuum are summarized, along with their correct result applied to space probes, while in Sect.III, the Starships are put into the dilatant vacuum framework and numerical results are discussed. Eventually, final considerations are presented in the conclusion.

II. Not negligible role of shear-thickening (dilatant) vacuum in space exploration missions

The Breakthrough Starshot project does not unfortunately take into account the important role of a recently discovered feature of physical vacuum, its dilatancy, proven by directly and exactly solving two famous anomalies, the Pioneer anomaly – previously and erroneously attributed to anisotropic heat dissipation [5–9]– and Mercury's perihelion precession, calculated via a relativistic equation which has now been derived from a modified Stokes' equation (MSE)

for dilatant vacuum [4]. The MSE has the following form

$$F_{\emptyset} = -6\pi r \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \kappa = -6\pi r (\gamma - 1) \kappa = -6\pi r D \kappa \quad (1)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor, κ is a unitary constant expressed in kg/s^2 , the subscript \emptyset refers to the vacuum and

$$D = \gamma - 1 \quad (2)$$

is the term of vacuum dilatancy.

This equation directly and exactly solves the anomalous acceleration of the Pioneer probes

$$a_p = \frac{F_{vac}}{m_p} = - \frac{6\pi r_p \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v_{max}}{c}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \kappa}{m_p} = - \frac{6\pi \cdot 1.371 \text{ m} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{36737 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}{299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \cdot 1 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}}{222 \text{ kg}} = -8.74 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}. \quad (3)$$

where $m_p = 222 \text{ kg}$ is the mass of the spacecrafts (258 kg) minus that of the burned fuel (36 kg hydrazine) after the Jupiter flyby; $r_p = 1.371 \text{ m}$ is the radius of the antenna (diameter is 9 ft) and $v_{max} = 36737 \text{ m/s}$ is the maximum speed of the probe, as indicated by NASA's Scientific and Technical Information Office [10] after the swing-by caused by Jupiter. Unfortunately, another probe which took advantage of the Jupiter flyby, the New Horizons spacecraft, was not Doppler tracked by NASA.

As shown in [4], the MSE also solves the anomalous precession of the planet Mercury (and the anomalous precessions of all planets, though less evident than that of Mercury) with total accuracy and it can be equated to Einstein formula for perihelia precession. Furthermore, the MSE correctly indicates stable orbits for the planets and allows to achieve a quantum formula for relativistic kinetic energy [11], an issue which is revealed as the necessary additional energy

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¹ A project by Breakthrough Initiatives: <https://breakthroughinitiatives.org/>

to oppose vacuum dilatancy

$$E_k = -\left(\frac{J_\theta^2}{2m} + J_\theta v_c\right) + \frac{1}{2}mv_o^2. \quad (4)$$

where $J_\theta = F_\theta \Delta t$ is the impulse caused by vacuum's reaction to shear stress, v_c is the maximum speed an accelerated body should achieve at a given energy according to classical physics and v_o is the observed maximum speed at the same given energy. Referring to Eq. 4, once the classical kinetic energy is subtracted and $J_\theta v_c$ (which is related to a quantum potential and does not apply to macroscopic objects) is set to zero (see [11]) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_k &= -\frac{J_\theta^2}{2m} = \\ &= -\left(-6\pi(1.371 \text{ m}) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{36737 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}{299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}\right)^2}} - 1\right) \cdot 1 \text{ s}\right)^2 \\ &\cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot 222 \text{ kg}} = -8.479 \times 10^{-17} \text{ J}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

which exactly corresponds to the deceleration detected by NASA via Doppler tracking

$$\begin{aligned} a_p &= -\frac{1}{\Delta t} \sqrt{\frac{2|\Delta E_k|}{m}} = -\frac{1}{1 \text{ s}} \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot (8.479 \times 10^{-17} \text{ J})}{222 \text{ kg}}} = \\ &= -8.74 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

On the contrary, Einstein formula for relativistic kinetic energy, once classical kinetic energy is subtracted, yields a largely wrong ΔE_k , because it ignores the energy amount referring to the second term of Eq. 4, which must be set to zero when acceleration of macroscopic bodies, for which the Stokes-Einstein radius is not applicable [11], is taken into account. The energy value yielded by Einstein equation is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_k &= E_k^{(rel)} - E_k^{(class)} = mc^2 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}} - 1\right) - \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \\ &= (222 \text{ kg})(299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1})^2 \cdot \\ &\cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{36737 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}{299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}\right)^2}} - 1\right) - \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(222 \text{ kg})(36737 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1})^2 = \\ &= 1687 \text{ J} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

which is extremely high (19 orders of magnitude higher than the correct value) and corresponds to the wrong acceleration of $-3.89 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, while the new quantum formula (4) yields the correct value. Pioneer probes, Mercury's perihelion precession, stable planetary orbits, relativistic kinetic energy: these evidences cannot be ignored and indicate the existence

FIG. 1. Plots of negative acceleration caused by dilatant vacuum, $a = F_\theta/m$, with fixed mass ($m = 0.002 \text{ kg}$) and different speed ranges.

of a dilatant vacuum, whose viscosity is probably rooted in the viscosity of the Higgs field (relativistic mass as a further mass-acquisition process, governed by the viscosity of the Higgs field?) or in dark matter particles diffused in a (super)fluid sea of dark energy, i.e. in an unexpected specific quantum hydrodynamic feature of the dark sector: the dilatancy of the cosmic mixture dark matter + dark energy.

III. Equations of dilatant vacuum applied to the Breakthrough Starshot mission

Let us proceed by putting the characteristics of the StarChips in the MSE. At the moment, the calculations are performed based on approximately deduced characteristics of the StarChips but small variations in the considered size or weight of the micro-probes do not make any important difference in indicating mission failure due to excessive deceleration caused by vacuum dilatancy. If we consider a total weight of about 2 g for a single StarChip, included a 16 m^2 lightsail, and therefore a radius (normalizing the lightsail to a circle) of 2.256 m, the unfortunate combination of ultra-light weight and a radius in the scale of meters allows vacuum's viscous force to provoke the following negative acceleration

$$\begin{aligned} a_{(StarChip)} &= \frac{F_\theta}{m} = -\frac{6\pi r \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{v_{max}}{c}\right)^2}} - 1\right) \kappa}{m} = \\ &= \frac{6\pi \cdot 2.256 \text{ m} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{44968868 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}{299792458 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}}\right)^2}} - 1\right) \cdot 1 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}}{0.002 \text{ kg}} = \\ &= -243.31 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

FIG. 2. Plot of $a = F_0/m$ where mass varies from 0.002 to 0.1 kg, reducing the effect of vacuum's viscous force.

if the micro probes travel at 15% of the speed of light. And they would be subject to a greater negative acceleration of -438m/s^2 , if traveling at 20% of the speed of light. A StarChip without lightsail, having mass 1 g and normalized radius of about 2.3 cm would be anyway subject to a deceleration of -9m/s^2 . This disadvantage will provoke mission failure and enormous wastefulness of financial resources. The problem is the erroneous belief that the lighter the mass the easier to accelerate a probe up to a considerable fraction of the speed of light. The classical fraction of kinetic energy increases of course with mass but the quantum fraction (vacuum's negative work done on the accelerated body) decreases with mass. Indeed, $a = F_0/m$ clearly indicates that a lighter mass causes higher deceleration of the probe. This

is the reason why planetary orbits are stable despite dilatant vacuum and why the much lighter Pioneer probe was, on the contrary, decelerated in a detectable way. Fig. 1 shows the negative acceleration for the StarChips, considering different speed ranges. Once the maximum speed of the Pioneer probe is reached, a StarChip would be decelerated ~ 171625 times the Pioneer probe. However, taking into account a speed of about 10^7 m/s along with a larger mass, for instance over 40 g, negative acceleration considerably decreases (see Fig.2). But at 20% of the speed of light it would be anyway 8.78m/s^2 and an even larger mass would be therefore necessary to minimize vacuum's viscous force. In practice, that means that a much greater energy amount is overall necessary for the Starshot programme and, based on current assumptions, that mission will fail.

IV. Conclusion

By applying the modified Stokes' equation for shear-thickening (dilatant) vacuum, a huge deceleration for ultralight objects traveling through the physical vacuum is predicted, which is also proportional to their section, normal to the direction of motion. Ultralight mass and large section (of the lightsail) exactly characterize the concept of the Breakthrough Starshot programme, for which the new equations for dilatant vacuum consequently indicate mission failure. Much larger mass for the probes would be necessary but in this case also much more energy, so the whole programme should be reconsidered from its theoretical foundations.

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